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Self-Actualization of a Young Teacher's Personality in Multicultural Educational Environment

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Abstract

The process of self-actualization of a teacher within a multicultural educational context creates the foundation for effective cross-cultural communication, tolerance, the development of professional multicultural competencies as well as fosters respect for ethnic minorities. This article demonstrates the importance of teacher self-actualization through the prism of scientific propositions. The latter implies the construction of a new theoretical framework, in which the teacher's personality is viewed as a "new" set of characteristics, personality traits and abilities necessary for the performance of professional activities. The materials provided in the article might be of interest for pre-school educators, child psychologists, university lecturers as well as for wider audiences.

The problem of the study lies in the fact that beginning teachers often fail to realize the full potential of their professional activities, thus raising the questions: what are the common features of a beginning teacher's personality self-actualization and who contributes to the improvement of quality of the educational process?

Keywords: teacher's personality, teacher development, beginning teacher, beginning teacher's adaptation, multicultural environment, teacher self-actualization, teacher induction.

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Introduction

Currently, the content of the teacher's personality self-actualization is a scientific theory, providing the definition of key concepts and statements that constitute the initial theoretical basis of science. The personality of the teacher is undergoing significant changes: the structure and requirements for the teacher are being transformed. Therefore, revealing the essence of the contemporary teacher, special attention is paid to the self-self-actualization of the personality of the teacher, particularly with regards to the beginning teachers. In the Education Dictionary, self-actualization is considered as a directed adaptation of the teacher to the conditions of a particular situation and the identification of reality with the activity of the subject (pupil / student), the absolutization of the activity principle (Zakirova, & Purik, 2016; Zakirova, & Gilmiyarova, 2016).

Following the idea of Kostyleva (2010), by the self-actualization of the teacher's personality we mean the multiple links of scientific proposition that presuppose the development of new theoretical foundations, where the self-self-actualization of the teacher's personality is not viewed just a set of characteristics, qualities and abilities necessary for carrying out professional activities. It is also derived from the profession-oriented personal characteristics of the young beginning teacher.

From the point of view of Zagoruli, self-actualization should also be understood as the creation of favorable duo-conditions for the "revealing" of the personality traits of both the pupil (student) and the realization of the potential of the young teacher.

Purpose and objectives of the study

One of the goals pursued by the self-actualization of the personality of a young beginning teacher in a multicultural environment is a shift from the individual to the universal, the formation of a particular type of reasoning that allows a teacher to identify oneself as a citizen of a country, a part of culture and social circle. The process of self-actualization of the personality of a teacher of a multicultural educational space includes national, cultural, civil and global levels.

The concept of teacher's personality self-actualization in the educational process is a complex, purposeful, dynamic system of fundamental knowledge about the phenomenon of self-actualization the creative potential of the teacher's personality in the educational process.

Thus, it can be said that the self-actualization of the personality of a young beginning teacher is not only a process of development of professional competencies, but also a process of building a personality of a young beginning teacher.

The process of self-actualization the personality of a young beginning teacher is determined by personality mechanisms such as freedom and responsibility. They form the "foundation" of the personality and play the role of the psychological "spine" on which all the other substructures are set. Freedom and responsibility are forms, ways of a human's existence in the world; the level of their development characterizes the civic-mindedness of the teacher. The teacher is responsible for his/her choice and is capable of reflection.

The second most important factor is the productive interaction of the personal and professional in the teacher. Abstract goals at this level are transformed into specific tasks of educational activity. The link between the personality of the teacher, his/her professional activity and culture is the awareness of the necessity of one or the other. A young beginning teacher determines the meaning and motives of

educational activity, educational policy, influences the choice of means and styles of educational management.

The third factor includes substructures that characterize typical for the teacher forms or ways of external manifestation of the personality in professional activity. This level includes: educational abilities, professional roles and attitudes, educational attitudes, psychological culture, etc. All of the above is subordinated to the highest levels of the teacher's personality and fulfill the performing function, which, in fact, justifies the need to study the higher manifestations of the teacher's personality, and thereby self-actualization of the teacher's personality.

Based on the above-mentioned factors, the value-oriented structure of the teacher's personality and the predominant type of orientation of educational communication are formed, which allows to distinguish the types of young beginning teachers.

The first type is characterized by low personal potential, where the underdevelopment of the potential for freedom and the potential for responsibility is combined with the destructive type of value-oriented structure of the teacher's personality at the predominantly pre-personal level. Such teachers are dominated by the conformal and authoritarian orientation of professional communication.

The second type reveals a misbalanced personal potential with an undeveloped potential for responsibility. This leads to the shift from freedom to arbitrariness and is conjugated with the value-oriented structure of the destructive type with a predominance of the egoistic level. The teachers of this type tend to demonstrate the manipulative approach to professional communication.

The third type of teachers is determined by the underdeveloped potential of freedom. This leads to the formation of false responsibility for other people's goals and values. The predominant type of orientation of professional communication among such teachers is indifferent. They strive to avoid communication at the personal level, replacing it with "business-like" communication at the level of social roles.

The fourth type is characterized by high personal potential, implying the full development of the potentials of freedom and responsibility, combined with the developing value-oriented structure of the teacher's personality. Teachers of this type are the only ones to follow the dialogical orientation of professional communication (Kostyleva, 2010).

The social attitude of the young teacher is unconditional. He/she is not only a provider of certain knowledge and meaningful information, but also a person responsible for the transfer of experience, traditions, recognized and generally accepted standards of behavior and interaction with others. The young beginning teacher should attitude him/herself as a mentor in the formation and development of the younger generation. Often, the attitude of authoritarian management has no chance of productive interaction with the student, because only a teacher who respects the personality of the student, regardless of the degree of his/her knowledge, degree of understanding or misunderstanding can deserve trust.

The attitude of the student's personality also changes/ it is no longer based on the results of learning and the assessment, but on active interaction with the teacher.

The nature of interaction is refracted: the so-called boundaries of the "weak" and "strong" are "erased", instead, the attitude of the democratic interactions of the teacher and the student is provided: collective empathy, cooperation, mutual assistance and help, creativity, attention to the personality's growth and initiative are pushed to the forth.

The literature research allows us to conclude that the definition of the self-actualization of the teacher's personality is in one way or another connected with the definition of the social attitude of the

teacher. From this point of view, the definition of Slastenin, where the attitude of the teacher is a set of intellectual, strong-willed, emotional and evaluative criteria for educational activity as a whole seems to be the most applicable. Many domestic and international researchers consider the self-actualization of the personality of the teacher through the attitude of professional self-determination of the young teacher.

A number of research emphasize that educational activity is a specifically personal education, expressing the professional attitude of each teacher. Professional and educational attitude is recognized as a characteristic that determines the choice of the subject of his/her future career, the implementation of activities, behavior, communication.

Methodology

The personality of the young teacher should be self-actualized through all educational functions: educational problem-solving, subject disciplines, extracurricular activities, etc. Teaching should consist of intense emotional intensity, lectures, debate, brainstorming, travel lessons, and the opening of world communities. In a multicultural context, one should study the main disciplines of Science, Arts and Humanities. A special role is assigned to the Arts: Culture Studies, Native and Foreign Languages, Literature, Psychology, Art, Sociology, History, etc.

Preliminary work should exclude mono-cultural approaches, introducing students-future teachers of the child environment to cultural differences, acmeological and axiological principles, poetics of ethnonational groups, outstanding artistic samples of different civilizations to demonstrate the universality of human nature.

Multicultural educational space is the union of all subjects of the educational process: teachers, students, parents, social and educational committees and partners of different ethnic groups. It presupposes the non-conflict interaction of the subjects of different ethnic groups on the basis of respect for universal, national and individual cultures. Multicultural educational space is a social and educational environment that reflects the particular characteristics of cultural diversity, contributes to the process of natural socio-cultural interaction of its participants. It is the multicultural space that is aimed at meeting the needs of young beginning teachers in obtaining education, supporting various ethnic communities and individuals that contribute to the establishment of dialogue, mutual enrichment and interaction of cultures (Gabdulchakov, 2015; Gabdulchakov, Galimova, & Yashina, 2016).

Based on the above mentioned, it can be emphasized that multicultural education for future teachers of the child environment is designed to help move from the individual to the universal, as well as form a special type of reasoning that will allow them to become a citizen, identify themselves with the cultural and social community, and develop the national and civil level of consciousness.

Results

The self-actualization of the teacher's personality in a multicultural educational environment implies the key role of a teacher. He/she should help students to determine their cultural identity, but at the same time explain the fact that everyone can be identified through several cultures, therefore, is the bearer of several identities. Many Russian and American researchers argue unanimously that a teacher's multicultural literacy begins with knowledge of the culture of his/her people (nationality, race, confession) and awareness of his/her cultural affiliation (Valeeva & Kalimullin, 2016).

Practicing teachers and researchers identify the core components of the self-actualization of the personality of a young beginning teacher in the Russian educational system: 1) the teacher's knowledge of

goals, basic ideas, concepts of preparing children for life and learning in general; 2) knowledge of cultural studies, ethics, ethno-psychology, the history of peoples and ethnic groups, demonstrating in the modern world the specifics of the cultural manifestations of the individual, group, society, providing an understanding of the importance of cultural diversity for the individual and society; 3) the ability to identify or make innovations in education, reflecting the ethnic and mental diversity of the surrounding world; 4), the ability to establish a cultural dialogue with representatives of other ethnic groups in the process of educational activity (Garifullina & Bashinova, 2017).

Our research allowed us to identify the following principles for the self-actualization of the personality of teachers to work in a multicultural child environment:

1. The principle of systematic multicultural training
2. The principle of informative multicultural training
3. The principle of self-management in multicultural training
4. The principle of socialization of multicultural training

The principle of systematic multicultural training should be understood as the regular study of the theory of multiculturalism, as well as the practical application of certain techniques and whole technologies of multicultural education in the pre-school.

The principle of informativeness presupposes the study of the latest theories and practices in the field of multicultural training of young teachers of child environment.

The principle of self-management implies the development of initiative and creativity of the young teacher. He/she should be smart in the implementation of certain projects, learn how to professionally approach the solution of the tasks assigned to him/her, and be able to master the situation. In their professional activities, a young beginning teacher is to possess the skills of self-management in order to implement multicultural approaches to dealing with children, parents, partners and social services.

The principle of socialization of multicultural training should be understood as the introduction of multicultural education ideas into the child environment in the preschool, explaining the global importance of multicultural training to their parents. Also, within the framework of multicultural education young teachers need to organize educational work with the teaching staff (conferences, discussions, meetings, exchange of experience, etc.).

However, there is a fundamental difference in the approaches of Russian and American researchers to educating students in a multicultural society. Russian researchers highlight the fundamental educational characteristics that will be required in practical activities; while American scholars, when approaching this issue, strive to form a responsible civic stand, the need to participate in political and managerial reforms of the country (Zakirova, & Purik, 2016; Zakirova, & Gilmiyarova, 2017).

The researcher A. Porter writes that all this is reminiscent of the “character of the Copernican revolution”, when the idea of the terminology of deviant behavior is shifted: “... to be ‘different’ and ‘strange’, since such characteristics have ceased to be dangerous or risky, perceived as a fashionable self-expression, an ideal way for personal growth in society. Acquaintance with the “alien” person, with radically different views on the world, approaches to solving some particular life problems, cultural background and upbringing, is perceived as a possibility of ‘unique’ interaction in the world of new values and patterns of behavior”[...].

In a contemporary society there is a need for the implementation of meaningful work on teacher training in the field of multicultural education, self-awareness, with a focus on moral values, as well as the search for methods appropriate to their professional training.

The problem of a young beginning teacher working in a multicultural child environment has certain differences in different regions of Russia. Today, the urgent task of creating a new education system, which will be built taking into account the specifics of local cultural and historical traditions, government programs, intellectual and resource potential is to be fulfilled.

Discussions

The ideas of multicultural education are not always positively evaluated in the global educational space. Often they are accused of mediocrity, considered too primitive, not relevant to modern realities. According to some practicing educators, multicultural training leads to the devaluation of ethnocultural similarities and differences, since the ideas of such education do not simply resolve cross-cultural conflicts, but rather increase the gap of misunderstanding between agents of cultural groups of the ethnic majority and minority.

Obviously, it is worth recognizing that the multicultural training of preschool education students may not be perfect.

There is some utopianism and idealization of multicultural training. However, it can also be noted here that the multicultural education is the future; these are certain potential opportunities for the implementation of cross-cultural dialogue in the educational system.

The success of a young beginning teacher in a multicultural environment will be the ability to analyze, critically evaluate any information, prevent the formation of various prejudices, and also remember that well-formed intracultural stereotypes affect harmonious intercultural dialogue. The

efficiency of multicultural education provide by a young beginning teacher depends on the consistency of the goals and objectives of vocational training, clarity and consistency of the requirements for the student.

The multicultural educational competence of a young beginning teacher is viewed as a unity of theoretical and practical readiness for activities in this environment. Besides knowledge and skills it also includes complex intellectual and practical skills. The multicultural competence of a young beginning teacher is an integrated result of learning activities in teaching practice and in extracurricular educational activities and is formed throughout the entire period of professional activity (Banks, 2004).

An absolutely new system of values is taking shape in the contemporary educational space: the concept of personality is reborn, acquiring individual nature conformity, suggesting new education paradigms, where educational reality is reflected through the new language of science. Such concepts as educational space, multi-ethnic state, multicultural educational environment, educational technologies, etc. have been introduced.

The third generation Russian Federal State Educational Standard of Higher Education for majors 44.03.01 "Education" and 44.03.02 "Education and Psychology" a Bachelor's Degree graduate is assigned qualifications "Academic Bachelor" and "Applied Bachelor". They are ready to solve such professional tasks as implementation of the rights of the child; creation of conditions for full-fledged training, education of students, interaction and communication of the child with peers and adults, socialization of students; participation in the creation of a psychologically comfortable and safe educational environment in the organization; increasing the level of psychological competence of participants in the educational process; participation in interdisciplinary psycho-educational and social rehabilitation activities in collaboration with related specialists; use of health-saving technologies in professional activities; the use of scientifically based methods and modern information technologies in the organization of their own professional activities; systematic improvement of their professional skills; compliance with professional ethics; increasing their own general cultural level; compliance with labor protection, safety and fire protection.

Educational activity in the child environment consists in the implementation of the process of training and education in accordance with the educational program of preschool education using psychologically grounded methods of training and education focused on the development of gaming activities; the creation of optimal conditions for the adaptation of children to pre-school educational organizations; ensuring the protection of life and health of children in the educational process; cooperating with other specialists (psychologist, speech therapist, pediatrician) and family; child's readiness to learn in a general education organization.

To obtain a Bachelor's Degree for majors 44.03.01 "Education" and 44.03.02 "Education and Psychology", the future teachers of the child environment are to develop general cultural (GCC), general professional (GPC), profession-oriented (POC) and professional-applied competences (PAC): the ability to use the basics of philosophical knowledge, analyze the main stages and patterns of historical development to understand the social significance of their activities (GCC-1); the ability to use the basics of economic knowledge in assessing the effectiveness of the results of activities in various fields (GCC-2); the ability of communication in oral and written forms in Russian and foreign languages for solving problems of interpersonal and cross-cultural interaction (GCC-3); ability to work in a team, tolerantly perceiving social, ethnic, confessional and cultural differences (GCC-4); ability for self-management and self-education (GCC-5); the ability to use general legal knowledge in various fields of activity (GCC-6); the ability to maintain an adequate level of physical wellness to ensure full social and professional activities (GCC-7); willingness to apply the basic methods of protecting industrial personnel and the public from the possible

consequences of accidents, disasters, natural disasters (GCC-8); possession of a historical method with its application to the assessment of socio-cultural phenomena (GCC-9); the ability to take into account the general, specific (for different types of violations) patterns and individual characteristics of mental and psychophysiological development, especially the regulation of human behavior and activity at different age levels (GPC-1); willingness to apply qualitative and quantitative methods of psychological and educational research (GPC -2); readiness to use methods of diagnostics of development, communication, activity of children of different ages (GPC -3), readiness to use knowledge of various theories of education, upbringing and development, basic educational programs for pre-school age (GPC -4); readiness to organize various types of activity: game, subject, productive, cultural and leisure (GPC -5); the ability to organize joint activities and interpersonal interaction of the subjects of the educational environment (GPC -6); the ability to conduct professional activities in a multicultural environment, taking into account the peculiarities of the socio-cultural development situation (GPC-9); readiness to apply in professional activities the main international and domestic regulation on the rights of the child (GPC -11); the ability to organize joint and individual activities of children in accordance with the age norms of their development (SCP-1); the ability to effectively interact with teachers of an educational institution and other specialists in the development of child play and learning activities (SCP-6); the ability to organize playful and productive activities of children of preschool age (PAC-1); readiness to implement professional tasks of educational, recreational and correctional and developmental programs (PAC -2); the ability to provide age-appropriate interaction of preschool children in child activities (PAC-3); willingness to ensure compliance with the educational conditions of communication and the development of preschool children in an educational organization (PAC -4); the ability to collect data on the individual characteristics of preschoolers, manifested in educational work and interaction with adults and peers (PAC -5); the ability to interact with the family, teachers and psychologists of the educational institution on the issues of education, training and development of preschool children (PAC -6) .

Studying the past experience of educational theory and practice of multicultural training of young teachers to work in a multicultural child environment shows that all stages of a multi-ethnic multicultural society, as well as gradually emerging problems of educating teachers to the values and people around them, are of paramount importance for society as a whole.

The self-actualization of the personality of a young beginning teacher in a child organization involves not only raising a loyal citizen of the Russian Federation, but also brings up the ability to cooperate with other nations, and also affects the young pedagogue of a multicultural environment for children such as tolerance towards others, respect for national differences, accept other ethnic groups as they are.

The main task today is the modernization of federal state standards, since they and the documents accompanying them are drawn up without taking into account the multicultural component in the field of vocational education. A decade earlier, the needs were completely different. Unequivocally the training of specialists of the XXIst century should be carried out taking into account the contemporary needs of society. The question of creating a new model of education based on multicultural orientation became topical at the end of the 20th century.

By the multicultural competence of young teachers to work in the multicultural child environment, we understand the readiness for transformation, creativity, initiative in the activities in the multicultural environment in the preschool educational organization. The unity of these indicators is expressed not only in knowledge and skills, but also in complex intellectual and practical skills.

Multicultural competence of young teachers to work in the multicultural child environment is a consistent, systematic and long-lasting result of the educational and extracurricular activities of students and continues to be formed throughout the entire period of study at the university.

The empathy inherent in young teaching staff of a multicultural child environment will positively affect their professional activities, allowing them to understand at a high level the national and regional specifics of relationships and behavior in preschool children, to coordinate joint activities with parents of different nationalities, to anticipate and prevent conflict situations in relationships. However, the ability to perceive and predict the behavior of students will manifest in practice among preschoolers to a greater extent than sensitivity to the intrapersonal national-specific qualities.

For young teachers working in a multicultural child environment with an insufficient level of multicultural skill, there will probably be no orientation towards the educational process taking into account national-psychological peculiarities; therefore, the educational activity is transformed into a socio-psychological communication.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we should give an example from the last stage of the experiment that we carried out, in which the significant value of the multicultural training of young teachers to work in the multicultural child environment was proved. The experimental group of young teachers was asked to write an essay on various topics that were united only on one basis - the teachers themselves had to choose topics from the proposed list. The control group of young teachers was asked to write an essay on the same topics from the proposed list, only the choice was left to the teacher. Each teacher had to describe his place and behavior in a particular event, life situations that occurred to him, curiosities, and more. In the experimental group, the topics closest to them were chosen and were able to put them on paper, while the control group's topics proposed by the teachers caused some difficulties and the presentation of the material was either written poorly or not written at all.

Thus, we can conclude that modern society is not enough just qualified preschool education specialists, there is a need for qualified teaching staff with training in the field of multicultural training, self-developing, with a focus on spiritual values, as well as looking for new working methods in the field of child environment.

The highest success in the multicultural environment of our region will be the ability of a young educator of a multicultural child environment to analyze, critically evaluate the incoming information, and also remember that well-formed intracultural stereotypes affect harmonious intercultural dialogue. The effectiveness of multicultural education depends on the consistency of the goals and objectives of vocational training, clarity and consistency of the requirements for a young beginning teacher of a multicultural child environment (Fahrutdinova, 2016).

The problem of multicultural training of a young beginning teacher to work in a multicultural child environment has certain differences in different regions of the Russian Federation. Today, the urgent task of creating a new education system, which will be built taking into account the specifics of local cultural and historical traditions, government programs, intellectual and resource potential is to be fulfilled.

The study proves that profession-oriented competencies are successfully developed through the optimal combination of active technologies in the course of multicultural education. These competencies are based on the ability to demonstrate a good understanding of the universality and national-cultural specifics of the linguistic picture of the world; apply theoretical knowledge and skills on the reflection of

the concept-sphere of ethnic consciousness in the linguistic picture of the world; use theoretical and practical knowledge in the field of intercultural communication for the development and application of original ideas in project activities; demonstrate communication skills and be able to apply them to solve problems related to cross-cultural communication; show a deep understanding of the universality and national-cultural specifics of the linguistic picture of the world; demonstrate a tolerant attitude and find solutions to non-standard situations in a multicultural and multi-ethnic environment; possess the linguo-didactic basics of using the Russian (and the second official - Tatar) languages as native and non-native in a multi-ethnic and multicultural environment; consciously apply knowledge in the field of comparative study of cultures in the process of interpreting artistic texts; interpret the features of the communicative behavior of representatives of different ethnic groups on the basis of cross-cultural research; explore the state of cross-cultural communication problems and demonstrate a critical assessment of the state of knowledge in this area; consciously apply the knowledge gained in a multi-ethnic education.

The literature study on the problem of the formation of a teacher's social attitude allows us to draw the following conclusions:

- the teacher's professional attitude acts as a system-forming category, as a factor in the development of the professional's personality, as the unity of professional consciousness and activity embodied in professional relationships and behavior, reflecting the teacher's main goal - to create conditions for the development of students in the process of their education and upbringing;

- the concepts of "educational attitude", "personal attitude" can claim to be equivalent to the integral personality of a teacher, since cover all levels of personality structure;

- the category of "educational attitude" is inextricably linked with the category of "educational activity". This is explained by the fact that the phenomenon of attitude is detected only through an activity (action, impact) or the potential of an activity; attitude contains a set of relations, which are mediated in activity manifestations;

- the essential characteristics of the attitude of the teacher are subject-orientation, activity, consciousness, freedom of choice of goals, methods and means of its implementation, responsibility, uniqueness, dynamism;

- the personal and professional attitude of the teacher has its own specifics. It lies in the fact that the attitude of the teacher towards himself as the subject of his own activity is connected with his attitude towards the students as subjects of their own activity;

These are implemented by the virtue of:

- humanitarian attitude of a teacher, where the "educational space of the meeting of generations" is created;

- educational attitude seen a unity of personal and professional attitudes;

- a teacher's personal and professional attitude viewed as a multifaceted concept reflecting various aspects of relationships

- the view of a teacher as a person with people (students, colleagues, etc.), with professional activities, with him/herself.

However, many aspects of multicultural teacher training remain unexplored: the concretization of educational results, taking into account the specific national and regional conditions of the constituent entities of the Russian Federation, the methodological tools for diagnosing educational results in multicultural education, the ratio of labor functions, actions and competencies. This will be the prospect of our further research.

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